

Entrepreneurship Potential Indigenous Martial Arts, Sports and Games of Manipur

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ABSTRACT: The meiteis play various martial arts, sports and games originated in the soil of their birth and treasured them as rich traditional heritage culture of the community since hoary past to till date. Sarit sarak, Mukhna, Mukhna Kangjei, Thang Ta, Sagol kangjei @ Polo, Kang @ Surface billiard, Ten Kappa, Ching kaba are some of the well known indigenous sports and games which are facing strong competition from modern sports games played and practice by the people of Manipur. In fact, indigenous sports and games are struggling for survival on its soil of birth. At this critical juncture, to save these indigenous activities from gradual extinction, Entrepreneurs can do Entrepreneurship program for these sports and games to save, preserve and popularize them through economic activities.

KEYWORDS: Sarit sarak (Defensive Offence and Capture), Mukhna (Manly body contact Trial of Stealth Strength between two Equal weight, height and age activity / meetei / Manipuri style wrestling), Mukhna Kangjei (Manly body contact Trial of Stealth Strength between two Equal weight, height and age activity / meetei / Manipuri style wrestling cum hockey), Thang Ta (Sword & Spear indigenous weapon system of the meetei), Sagol kangjei (Hockey on Horse Back @ Horse Hockey @Polo), Kang (Surface billiard played with oblong shaped flat object), Ten Kappa (Arrow shooting), Ching kaba (Mountain climbing @ Mountaineering), Entrepreneurs , Entrepreneurship, Indigenous, Extinction.

INTRODUCTION

Manipur a small state in physical territory, it is home to nearly 50 plus colourful talented communities having different traditional cultural heritage and the Meetei is one such community among them having rich traditional cultural heritage of high end esteem as the other communities do. They play different form of dare devil indigenous games even today that people from across the globe watch in awe anywhere whenever they are on display as stage performance program. These activities has millions years history of existence (Pre history to till date), but began to become a group dying activities with the entry of modern sports and games in the state.

Though the people of the land loved and adored these activities but they cannot remain confining in its limited avenue because of its amateurism character. Only the few diehards belonging to well to do middle class and royal families can remain with indigenous activities. For the poor people, though they have immense love for indigenous games and sports sector, they prefer to opt for modern games and sports like Archery, Athletics, Boxing, Cricket, Football, Judo, Weightlifting, etc because once they succeed in carving a niche in the game, life turns a full cycle. Recognition, name fame, and money began to knocking at the door. Besides, imported modern games & sports are more recreational, fan following, easy to learn and performed activities than the indigenous activities. Success in modern games helps the players earning easy life and livelihood at the state and national establishments of the nation. Further, through modern games recognized by the National Olympic Association medal events in the national, continental, world cup and Olympic games, there is every possibility for carving a niche at the national, international, Asian games and Olympics and world cup level, etc.

Sarit sarak (Defensive Offence and Capture), Mukhna (Manly body contact Trial of Stealth Strength between two Equal weight, height and age activity / meetei / Manipuri style wrestling), Mukhna Kangjei (Manly body contact Trial of Stealth Strength between two Equal weight, height and age activity / meetei / Manipuri style wrestling cum hockey), Thang Ta (Sword & Spear indigenous weapon system of the meetei), Sagol kangjei (Hockey on Horse Back @ Horse Hockey @Polo), Kang (Surface billiard played with oblong shaped flat object), Ten Kappa (Arrow shooting), Ching kaba (Mountain climbing @ Mountaineering), became a victim of choice as most of them are not recognize by the Indian Olympic Association, International Olympic Committee and Ministry of Youth Affairs & Sports, Government of India. Another reason for fading away of these activities is that people of different age group in Manipur has opted modern foreign sports and games instead of indigenous activities.

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Another reason is that there is no indigenous sports equipment manufacturing factory and industry of any scale from where it can be sold in the market as the modern games and sports does. While entering the state, modern games and sports landed here with necessary equipments, gears and standardize set of rules & regulations that allowed the local people easily accessible to it. In other words, with their arrival, sports equipments shops began to crop up in every big and small towns of the state that attract large number of interested individual. Further, the easily adaptable character of the people also made them handy in mastering the skill, techniques and tactics of playing such activities while indigenous martial arts, sports and games has hardly any recognizable standard equipment production houses in the state as well set rules for playing them in standard format.

Significance of the study

The significance of the study is that

1. It helps to find out which activity requires what kind of equipments and how it can be developed and improved in standardise fashion for necessary use in the events of organise competitions where nobody would raise any question against the equipments.
2. It will provide essential helps to the lovers of indigenous games and sports as well as martial arts to explore a way out and means to save these activities from gradual disappearance from the society at large.
3. It will help and encourage the individuals who are interested in taking up the cudgel of entrepreneurship for saving it through business activities and promotion & popularisation to posterity.
4. It will help in identifying the kind of equipments use for playing different indigenous games & sports and martial arts as well as safety gears and garments, etc.

Objectives of the study

1. It is to highlight the plight of Indigenous Games & Sports and Martial Arts of Manipur and the need for immediate attention to save it from gradual dying present and disappearance from the society.
2. It is to explore the practical probability of every possible economic activities and business opportunities that can be figure out from the Indigenous Games & Sports and Martial Arts of Manipur.

Hypothesis of the study

1. There will be enough area for business probability and opportunities if anybody dares to make out good enough return from it.
2. There will be enough avenues of sponsors for those who wanted to venture into the field of Entrepreneurship Potential Indigenous Games & Sports and Martial Arts, of Manipur.
3. It will provide any individual and interested communities enough opportunities to do Entrepreneurship.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methods adopted for data collection of this precise paper is a combine method of descriptive, observation and spot visit, personnel interview of the concern authorities of the indigenous Martial Arts, Sports and Games of Manipur and archival study etc. Information related with the study have been collected after rounds of survey and necessary archival study base comparative activities to give the study a finishing touch.

EQUIPMENTS FOR INDIGENOUS MARTIAL ARTS, SPORTS AND GAMES

Among the ages old indigenous games & sports and martial arts believed played and practice in the state since time immemorial, Mukna @ Meetei style wrestling, Mukna (Meetei style wrestling) Kangjei the play activity of hockey played holding a season root mallet, Thang (sword) Ta (Spear), Sagol kangjei @ Polo, Kang @ Surface billiard, Ten Kappa @ modern archery @ Indian round archery activities, it requires necessary sports garments, equipments and protective gears, etc.

1. Mukna (Manly body contact Trial of Stealth Strength between two Equal weight, height and age activity / meetei / Manipuri style wrestling),: (Mukhna @ Manipuri style wrestling / Trial of strength body contact sports.

2. Mukna Kangjei (Manly body contact Trial of Stealth Strength between two Equal weight, height and age activity / meetei / Manipuri style wrestling): (Manly body contact Trial of Stealth Strength between two Equal weight, height and age activity / meetei / Manipuri style wrestling) a strong cane stick having season root head on the striking end for striking ball) and ball.

3. Thang-Ta (Sword-Spear): This is an indigenous weapon (sword and spear made of iron metals) using martial arts where the opponents or performers are displaying their skill prowess in the process of duals or compose fights. Chung/chungkoi @ Shield/buckle is an indispensable weapon of both the fighters/performers.

4. Sagol kangjei @ Polo: It is another world conquering indigenous game of Manipur carried away by the British officers as their favorite past time game there they named it Polo. A game played by mallet wielding men / women sitting on the horse back competed to score by striking the ball towards opponent team's goal post.

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5. Kang @ Surface billiard: Kang is a flat oblong object made from resin/ivory/bauxite use to play the game of Kang. The game kang is literally meaning surface billiard where every player would try to score points by throwing the oblong flat object towards the target @ a spherical sphere @ ball place on the other non striking end.

6. Ten Kappa @ (Arrow shooting) @ target archery: Archery @ Arrow shooting from Bow @ Ten Kappa is an Indispensable part of ritual ceremonial tradition of meetei communities especially in birth rituals or first ceremony after birth. In the process of birth rituals, when the moment arrives, the maternal uncle at the advice of the conduct authority the Amaiba (priest) sanctifies himself with the water from the holy pot and offer flowers to the bow & arrows and took them, goes outside the house in the frontal lawn, there the Amaiba (priest) spelling the related invocation hymns offer flowers to the arrows then the maternal uncle starts shooting the arrows to different directions, first to the Chingkhei (God of the East), second arrow to the Thangjing (God of the West), third to the Wangbren (God of the South) and fourth arrow to the Koubru (God of the North). The process concluded with the last and fifth arrow aimed at the sky and then to the earth seeking prosperous life of the child. Then, touching the frontal door with the arrow, he enter inside the house and places the 5th arrow near the Holy Pot offering it to the Almighty God (Chingu-Nongdamba) and Goddess (Chingu-Nongdambi), the supreme god and goddess who the meetei believed determine the fate of mankind.

Then, the parents of the child offer their gratitude with Akatsen (dakhsina), a kind of ritualistic offering of cash, usually coins to the maternal uncle who in turn offer the child signifying it a blessing of wealth to the child. The same is followed by the father, mother, friends and relatives and others who come to attain the ritual blessing wishing ceremony for long life, wisdom, health, wealth and prosperity to the child (Physical realities).

Coincidentally, it happens an International as well as Olympic medal event but due to its expensive nature, the beginners did not find easy to train themselves for reaching Olympic round. Hence, the invention of Take down Bamboo Bow and Arrows design and produce here in Manipur help archers in the nation climbing the stairs upto Olympic Games. It's a reality and fact.

Identification of the required Protective Gears & Equipment

Sl.	Activity	Protective gears	Equipments
1	Mukhna	Mukhna costume/ sports garments	n/a
2	Mukhna Kangjei	Mukhna costume	1. Cane stick having season root head on the striking end for striking ball) and ball. 2. Ball
3	Thang Ta	1. Full body protection equipment. 2. Head gear 3. Chest guard 4. Wrist band/guard 5. Leg guard	1. Sword. 2. Spear 3. Shield/buckle 4. Sword spear holder
4	Sagol kangjei	1. Uniform as per set rules of IPA. 2. Helmet 3. Knee high boot	1. Pony 2. Saddles 3. Rein 4. Whips 5. Horse Shoes 6. Hockey sticks & Balls.
5	Kang	Traditional attires as per mutual agreement	1. Kang @ Oblong shaped palm size flat object. 2. Kangkhin @ Glass ball
6	Ten Kappa	Traditional or modern attires as per mutual agreement or set rules of FITA	1. Bow 2. Arrows 3. Quivers 4. Target bust
7	Indian Round Archery sports	Traditional or modern attires as per mutual agreement or set rules of FITA	5. Bow 6. Arrows 7. Quivers 8. Target bust

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DESCRIPTION OF THE EQUIPMENTS ACTIVITY WISE

Mukhna: To play the game / sport of mukhna literally meaning manly body contact Trial of Stealth Strength between two Equal weight, height and age activity of meetei / Manipuri style wrestling), in short, Mukhna @ Manipuri style wrestling / Trial of strength body contact sports, the players wears thick and tightly stitch inner garments and around it, they put on Kisi (Knot) phijet (costume) @ Kisi phijet @ Knotted costume. It is prepared using traditionally weaved of cotton yarn cloth which not less than two half arm length in breath and seven half arm length in length. The cloth is squeezed into a punch hole size rope and tied around above the waist and bonded in the form of a tight knot at the navel line and dropped the remaining part from the navel line in the front only to pull up tightly between the buttocks to bind its tail tightly with a knot just at the back bone line that form a shape of bodyline rope.

Mukhn Kangjei

To play the game of mukhna kangjei, the player wore same costume of mukhna player. Each player play the game using a strong cane stick having season root head on the striking end for striking the ball. They play the game by hitting the ball but after overcoming and over powering their opponents by means of mukhna techniques.

Thang-Ta (Sword-Spear): To play this indigenous weapon system of sword and spear made of iron metals, each player wore Thang Ta Phijet literally meaning costumes of sword spear martial arts generally of black colours. They use protective gears like Kok yom (head gears), khutyom (arm bands) and khongyom (leg bands). They play/perform the art using yot thang (metal swords) of different designs and size, Ta (spears) and Chung/Chungkoi (Shield/buckle). Weapon used to play or perform this martial arts of Thang Ta duals are, Thangsang (Long sword), Chungkoi (Shield/Buckle) and Ta (spear) using martial arts where the opponents or performers are displaying their skill prowess in the process of duals or compose fights.

Equipments for Thang Ta Martial Arts are Full body protection equipment. Head gear, Chest guard, Wrist band/guard and Leg guard, etc.

Sagol kangjei @ Polo: To play the game of polo each player has to ride a horse. Players of this game needed to be an excellent horse rider as well as expert polo player. Polo players are a combine product of man and beast i.e horse & the rider form a single unit to play the game. The players wore modern polo playing protective gears including helmets, long boots, hand gloves, etc. They owned polo playing personnel horses pony @ horses and train them to play excellent sagol kangjei/polo, Saddles, Rein, Whips, Horse Shoes and Hockey sticks & Balls.

Kang @ Surface billiard: Kang is a flat oblong object made from resin/ivory/bauxite use to play the game of Kang. To play the game kang the equipments required are Kang @ Oblong shaped palm size flat object, Kangkhin @ Glass ball.

Ten Kappa @ (Arrow shooting) @ target archery: Archery @ Arrow shooting from Bow @ Ten Kappa is an Indispensable part of ritual ceremonial tradition of meetei communities especially in birth rituals or first ceremony after birth as well as Olympic sports. The equipments required to play the sport are Bow, Arrows, Quivers and Target bust, etc.

ENTREPRENEURS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP A CALL OF THE HOURS

People often talk on topics like rich traditional cultural heritage of martial arts, sports and games of Manipur, need for promotion of indigenous games & sports, Manipur is the powerhouse of the region and nation etc, etc but nobody including the government establishment, universities dare to take responsible step towards preservation, promotion and popularization of these activities so that it can move upwards into international recognition and acceptance like Greco Roman Wrestling, Taekwondo, Judo and Wushu etc in a refine manner.

For preservation, promotion and popularization of these activities, Entrepreneurs can do Entrepreneurship program for these sports and games, and save them for posterity. Interested individual can go for Skill India Start Up program with full dedication.

For target archery there is handful of small and medium Entrepreneurs in the state whose production is reaching most of target archery avenues of the nation and sub continent.

IN FINE

No business or venture is free from risks and problems. From problems only, prospects emerge and that is the real beginning of a business set up. Hence, it is worthy to assume that Entrepreneurship is the branded activities of Entrepreneurs who never ceases looking for business opportunities in the market but sitting on the mount of problems.

REFERENCES

- 1) Nintthoujam Dhiren Singh, Chaoba The Bowyer of Manipur and His All Archery Families (Published Book-2006)
- 2) My Vision For A Shining Manipur (Published Book-2018)
- 3) Manipur Sports and Tourism Policy Concern (Published Seminar paper-2013)
- 4) Academic Reforms In Curriculum and Pedagogy in Manipur context (Published Seminar paper-2010-11)

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- 5) Entrepreneurship opportunities of Bamboo Base Archery Sports Equipment in Manipur (Published International Seminar paper 2019-20).
- 6) Physical realities in Manipur.
- 7) Roving Report ANI, October 2017.
- 8) All Manipur Archery Association (Estd: 1972).
- 9) B. Chaoba Sharma, the winner of 1st Governor Innovation Award, Manipur, 2018.
- 10) Google wikepeida and you tube.
- 11) The Telegraph News